

MULTIFUNCTIONALITY OF INTEGRATION IN THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *The article discusses the relevance of creating an integrative educational environment in educational organizations, which is considered as a set of certain interrelated factors (conditions) that influence a person's education. The environment of this environment is determined by the mutual influence, interaction and involvement of the subject of the educational environment in these processes. The author believes that this context is determined by the existence of a certain subjective position of the student. Integration then acts as an objective factor in the implementation of a number of principles and functions of this environment. Integration in this context determines the holistic characteristics of the educational environment and acts as a condition, principle, method and means, which reveals the peculiarity of the multifunctionality of integration. The author of the article reveals the concepts: condition, principle, method and means and their essence in defining integration itself. The multifunctionality of the educational environment, from the author's point of view, will ensure the ability of subjects to think systematically when implementing the highest level of interaction, characterized by the success and creative activity of a modern person (graduate of an educational organization), a specialist (head of an educational organization, teacher) in the transformation (development) of society into in accordance with universal human values. In addition, the teaching staff of an educational organization, when creating an integrative educational environment, actualizes the search for effective content, methods, techniques, forms of organizing training, social and pedagogical contacts of all participants in the educational process, and evaluation criteria, which actualizes the formation of original pedagogical and management technologies in education.*

Keywords: multifunctionality of integration, integrative educational environment, subject position, condition, principle, method, means.

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается актуальность создания в образовательных организациях интегративной образовательной среды, которая рассматривается как совокупность определенных взаимосвязанных факторов (условий), оказывающих влияние на образование человека. Окружение данной среды обусловлено взаимовлиянием, взаимодействием и включенностью в эти процессы субъекта образовательной среды. Автор считает, что данный контекст определяется существованием определённой субъектной позиции обучающегося. Интеграция тогда выступает объективным фактором и реализации ряда принципов и функций этой среды. Интеграция в этом контексте определяет целостную характеристику образовательной среды и выступает как условие, принцип, способ и средство, что раскрывает особенность полифункциональности интеграции. Автор статьи раскрывает понятия: условие, принцип, способ и средство и их сущность в определении самой интеграции. Полифункциональность образовательной среды, с точки зрения автора, и обеспечит способность субъектов системно мыслить при реализации самого высокого уровня взаимодействия, характеризующегося успешностью и творческой активностью современного человека (выпускник образовательной организации), специалиста*

(руководитель образовательной организации, педагог) по преобразованию (развитию) общества в соответствии с общечеловеческими ценностями. Кроме того, педагогический коллектив образовательной организации при создании интегративной образовательной среды актуализирует поиск эффективного содержания, методов, приемов, форм организации обучения, социально- педагогических контактов всех участников образовательного процесса, оценочных критериев, что актуализирует формирование авторских педагогических и управленческих технологий в образовании.

Ключевые слова: полифункциональность интеграции, интегративная образовательная среда, субъектная позиция, условие, принцип, способ, средство.

The main task of Russian educational policy is to ensure modern quality of education based on maintaining its fundamental nature and compliance with the current and future needs of the individual, society, and state. The basis for the implementation of the state’s educational policy is determined by social targeting and balance of social interests, issues of improving the pedagogical skills of the teacher.

Consequently, an educational organization must organize an environment for the development of the student’s personality, combining approaches focused on various pedagogical paradigms.

Thus, the problem of creating an integrative educational environment is being updated, which is considered as a set of certain interrelated factors (conditions) that can influence a person’s education. The concept of environment presupposes the presence of an environment. Speaking about the environment, we mean the mutual influence, interaction of the environment and the object in question (in our case, the student) located in this environment (V. G. Vorontsova, V. A. Kozyrev, A. P. Tryapitsyna, etc.) [3, 6.9]. In this case, the inclusion of the student in this environment, his certain subject position, is mandatory. The subjective positions of the student as a learner and self-organizer, the subjective positions of the teacher as a learner, self-organizer and teacher are a serious subject of research, since the integration of the subjective positions of each subject affects equally both the professional development of the teacher himself and the development of the student’s personality [1 ,6].\

Integration in the educational process of an educational institution ensures the implementation of such principles as: methodological, professional orientation, systematizing, integrity, polytechnicism, problem-solving, aimed at the implementation of teaching, educational and developmental functions.

The objective factors of integration are, according to researchers: the law of the universal connection of phenomena, time as a factor in the compaction of life experience, an increase in the volume of information, the need for creativity based on stable experience, and the intensive nature of education. In addition, most studies devoted to the development of integration theory draw attention to the fact that human activity is integrative in its essence. But it realizes its integrativeness only by shaping specific types of activities through the unity of universality and universality, aimed at specific subject areas of activity (Kiketz G. Yu. et al.) [3,4,9].

A.A. Danilyuk in his research notes that “integration is the peak of creative self-development of traditional education, an attempt of traditional pedagogy to overcome itself, to decisively reconsider its own foundations: the scientific nature and didactic disunity of academic disciplines, the mechanical sequence of lessons abstracted from life, and, above all, from life child” [2].

Meanwhile, when considering integration as a characteristic of the educational environment, it is necessary to take into account its multifunctionality, which in theory and practice is considered as a condition, principle, method and means.

Expanding these functions, let us turn to the essence of these concepts that are closest to our problems.

The concept of “condition” is most often considered as: circumstances on which something else depends (conditioned) or the environment in which something happens. Conditions are considered external and internal, where external (practical) are types of activities, their objects, actions, operations, means and results; internal (personal) is the personality of its components, namely: motives, values, attitudes, personal goals of activity [5,10]. Consequently, if integration is considered as a condition, then integration refers to external conditions as the principle of implementing these conditions, and to internal conditions integration as a method and means.

The principle in various sources is considered as the initial position of the organization or the internal conviction of a person. In the problem under consideration, we assume that the first position includes the organization of learning itself, and the second - the interaction of subjects of the educational process [5,7,8].

The method is most often considered as the development of any activity [5,7,8]. Thus, these are changes in the activities of all subjects of the educational process (student, teacher, parent, leader) when organizing training.

And finally, the concept of “means” is considered as a holistic knowledge of the world, oneself; the ability to think systematically when solving practical problems [5,7,8,10]. Thus, integration is a means of influencing the subject’s self-determination (life, personal and professional).

So, an educational environment where integration is realized in an integral system, namely its multifunctionality, in our opinion, will ensure the ability of subjects to think systematically when implementing the highest level of interaction, characterized by the success and creative activity of a modern person (graduate of an educational organization), specialist (manager educational organization, teacher) for the transformation (development) of society in accordance with universal human values [6]. Consequently, we are talking about successful, educated, creatively independent and adaptable participants in the educational process who are humanists, democrats, and citizens of their country. This environment will create conditions for the development of all participants in the educational process (leader, teacher, student, parent).

The focus of the teaching staff of an educational organization on creating an integrative educational environment actualizes the search for effective content, methods, techniques, forms of organizing training, social and pedagogical contacts of all participants in the educational process, evaluation criteria, etc. In addition, the integrative educational environment actualizes the transfer to the head of the educational organization, teacher authorial, and not just performing powers; creation of intensive, accompanying forms of scientific and methodological work; a change in professional managerial and pedagogical thinking in the creation of real examples of experience that has no analogues in science and practice.

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